

Chemically Engineered GaN Thin Films for Light-Stimulated Artificial Synapses

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The conventional von Neumann architecture is increasingly losing the capacity to satisfy the urgent demand for high-speed parallel computing, energy efficiency, and ultralow power consumption owing to the rapid growth of information. Brain-inspired neuromorphic computing presents an opportunity to overcome the inherent limitations of conventional computers. In recent years, photoelectric neuromorphic devices have garnered significant attention for their potential applications in brain-machine interfaces, intelligent sensing, and neuromorphic computing. Herein, a simple two-terminal light-stimulated synaptic device is fabricated using GaN thin films through metal-organic chemical vapor deposition. The device demonstrates the ability to mimic various biological synaptic functions, including learning-experience behavior, the transition from short-term to long-term memory, paired-pulse facilitation, and visual recognition and memory. In this research, an effective strategy for developing photonic synapses using GaN-based materials in neuromorphic computing and bio-realistic artificial intelligence systems is presented.

systems predominantly rely on complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor devices. However, this technology faces challenges related to power consumption and switching speed, limiting its ability to meet the growing requirements for computational and storage capacities.^[1] In contrast, the human brain demonstrates extremely high storage capacity and computational speed, capable of directly processing and storing optical images with high parallelism and fault tolerance.^[2] The human brain comprises $\approx 10^{15}$ synapses and 10^{11} neurons, with synapses playing an important role in information transmission between neurons.^[3] Therefore, developing artificial synaptic devices that emulate the behavior of neural synapses is essential for the hardware implementation of brain-inspired computing.

Over the past decade, numerous types of synaptic devices have been proposed, including memristors,^[4] transistors,^[5] magnetic devices,^[6] and ferroelectric memory.^[7] In comparison to electrically stimulated synaptic devices, light-stimulated synaptic devices are better suited for ultrafast computation due to their remarkable characteristics such as

1. Introduction

With the advancement of the Internet of Things and artificial intelligence, the demand for computing and storage is rapidly increasing across various fields. Current data processing

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DOI: 10.1002/adpr.202400146

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low power consumption, high immunity to interference, and low cross talk.^[8] Neural computing systems based on light-stimulated synaptic devices, in particular, mimic the human visual system by sensing, processing, and storing optical information, showing significant potential in fields such as image recognition, optical communication, and autonomous driving.^[9,10] A variety of active materials have been demonstrated to exhibit light-stimulated synaptic properties, such as metal oxides,^[11] perovskites,^[11b,12] organic materials,^[13] 2D materials,^[14] and III–IV semiconductors.^[15] Among these, gallium nitride (GaN)-based materials consisting of III–V semiconductors have stable and sustained persistent photoconductivity (PPC) behavior at room temperature,^[16] high photoelectric conversion efficiency, a tunable direct bandgap, and compatibility with semiconductor technology.^[17] However, there are very few reports available on the light-stimulated synaptic properties of GaN-based devices. Han et al. successfully realized a simple, two-terminal light-stimulated synaptic device based on GaN thin films (TFs).^[15a] Zhou et al. reported that the energy consumption of a single-GaN–nanowire synaptic device can be reduced to 2.72×10^{-12} J.^[18] Due to their simple preparation and outstanding performance, GaN materials are emerging as a promising option for light-stimulated synaptic devices. Despite the remarkable advantages of GaN-based neuromorphic devices and notable research progress, there are still a great many unexplored fields. As is widely known, doping is a straightforward and crucial method for modulating and improving the electrical and optical characteristics of semiconductors. Silicon and magnesium are the main impurities for obtaining n-type and p-type conductivity in GaN materials, respectively, and they are widely used in the industry.^[19] Unfortunately, the influence of these two impurities on the synaptic device performance of GaN is not well understood. In previous work, although some influences of Si on synaptic performance were studied, the doping concentration of Si could not be precisely controlled by the growth method of magnetron sputtering.^[15a] It is of great necessity to systematically investigate the role of Si and Mg doping on the light-stimulated synaptic properties.

Herein, we employed metal-organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) to grow Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN TFs on sapphire substrates. We then fabricated metal–semiconductor–metal (MSM) two-terminal optoelectronic artificial synaptic devices using an Ag/GaN/Ag structure. Among the

three types of doping, the Si-doped GaN device demonstrated diverse biological synapse-like functions, including transition from short-term memory (STM) to long-term memory (LTM), paired-pulse facilitation (PPF), and learning behavior. This work presents a straightforward and efficient strategy for developing light-stimulated synaptic devices for high-performance neuromorphic computing.

2. Results and Discussion

Figure S1a, Supporting Information, shows X-Ray diffraction (XRD) patterns (ω - 2θ) for Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN TFs formed on the (0001) sapphire substrates. The (0002) and (0004) peaks corresponding to GaN and (0006) peak for the sapphire substrate are observed in the 2θ scan. The results confirmed the wurtzite c-axis growth orientation and the hexagonal nature of GaN TFs. Correspondingly, the doping profiles tested by secondary-ion-mass spectrometry (SIMS) indicated that Mg and Si doping concentration levels were $\approx 2 \times 10^{18}$ at cm^{-3} , as shown in Figure S1b, Supporting Information.

Figure S2, Supporting Information, presents the surface morphology images of Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN TFs. The scan area is $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$. All of the TFs had a smooth surface, and the root-mean-square values were 0.18, 0.17, and 0.17 for Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN TFs, respectively. The terrace structure and some pits caused by dislocations were observed. These results revealed that there was a slight difference in surface morphologies between the Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN TFs. Figure 1a shows the Raman spectral data of Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN TFs. The Raman spectra showed two peaks, denoted as the symmetry-allowed phonon modes E_2 (high) and longitudinal optical phonon modes A_1 (LO). These two typical peaks indicated C-axis oriented wurtzite structure, which aligned with the XRD patterns. The E_2 (high) peak positions of the Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN TFs were all $\approx 570.61 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and the line widths of the E_2 modes in the three samples were also nearly the same. The E_2 (high) phonon mode is considered to be highly responsive to the biaxial stress in the crystal.^[20] Therefore, the impurity concentrations of Si and Mg used in this study ($\approx 2 \times 10^{18}$ at cm^{-3}) had a slight effect on the stress in the epilayers. Generally, the E_2 (high) peak is considered to be particularly sensitive to the stress in GaN.

Figure 1. Raman spectra a) and photoluminescence spectra b) for Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN layers at ambient temperature.

The E_2 peak of stress-free GaN is typically considered to be at 566.2 cm^{-1} .^[21] According to the stress equation^[20a] and the measured data, the calculated stresses for the three samples were $\approx 1.02\text{ GPa}$ corresponding to 570.61 cm^{-1} , indicating that Mg and Si impurities have little effect on the stress of the GaN film using the MOCVD growth process in this study. The $A_1(\text{LO})$ mode, in contrast to the E_2 (high) mode, is less influenced by compressive stress, with its frequency primarily determined by the coupling between the plasmon macroscopic and LO phonon longitudinal fields. As a result, the characteristics of the $A_1(\text{LO})$ mode are heavily dependent on the free-carrier concentration due to this phonon–plasmon interaction. Specifically, as the carrier concentration increases, the $A_1(\text{LO})$ peak broadens, and its frequency rises.^[22] The Raman spectral data indicated that the $A_1(\text{LO})$ peak positions of Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN TFs were 736.22 , 735.99 , and 735.49 cm^{-1} , respectively. The $A_1(\text{LO})$ peak for Si-doped and Mg-doped GaN TFs shifts slightly toward higher wavenumbers, owing to the high carrier concentration introduced by Mg and Si doping. The larger full-width at half-maximum and lower intensity of the Si-doped GaN sample indicated the presence of more defects compared to Mg-doped and undoped GaN samples.^[23]

In the photoluminescence (PL) spectrum (Figure 1b), all three samples showed dominant emission peaks at 365 nm , which is due to band-edge-related emission and is considered an intrinsic emission band. The highest intensity observed in the Si-doped sample is attributed to the higher electron concentration in the conduction band compared to the Mg-doped and undoped GaN samples. The Si-doped GaN sample exhibited yellow

luminescence (YL) compared with the Mg-doped and undoped GaN samples, with YL bands located at $\approx 2.25\text{ eV}$ (550 nm). The YL peak is likely associated with deep-level states within the energy band. It is generally accepted that the optical transitions responsible for YL are caused by a combination of factors, including Ga vacancies, C impurities, edge dislocations, and other defects, rather than a single impurity.^[23] Therefore, the highest YL intensity observed in the Si-doped GaN sample is due to the presence of more defects, which is consistent with the results from the Raman spectra.

Neurons, the fundamental nerve cells in the human brain, are interconnected via synapses.^[24] The neural system can transmit and process information through these neurons and synapses.^[9a,24,25] A schematic illustration of biological synapses is shown in the upper part of Figure 2d. When an action potential achieves the presynaptic terminal, voltage-gated Ca^{2+} channels open, which allows Ca^{2+} ions to enter the presynaptic membrane. This influx of Ca^{2+} can trigger the release of neurotransmitter vesicles into the synaptic cleft, where neurotransmitters bind to receptors on the postsynaptic membrane. This binding alters the electrical conductivity of the synapse, manifesting as an excitatory postsynaptic current (EPSC).^[15b] To replicate this biological process, we developed two-terminal optoelectronic artificial synaptic devices with an Ag/GaN/Ag structure. In these devices, the two Ag electrodes and the GaN layer function as the presynaptic/postsynaptic membranes and the synaptic cleft, respectively. Upon illumination, photogenerated carriers within the device act as neurotransmitters, transmitting information. The lower part of Figure 2d illustrates the light-stimulated

Figure 2. EPSC characteristics of a) undoped, b) Mg-doped, and c) Si-doped GaN TFs. d) Schematic illustration of the synaptic device and the biological synapse. Inset graphs in (a–c) show the fitting curves using the Kohlrausch-stretched exponential function. Each light excitation pulse lasts for 10 s under 360 nm wavelength light exposure, with an intensity of 1.33 mW cm^{-2} , and a bias voltage of 0.01 V .

synaptic device. As with biological synapses, the EPSC of the device varies with light-induced charge migration. Figure 2a–c shows the typical current response of the device to a 0.01 V read voltage and 360 nm light at an intensity of 1.33 mW cm^{-2} for undoped, Mg-doped, and Si-doped GaN TFs, respectively. After 10 s of illumination, the EPSC changes were 0.038, 0.046, and $0.206 \mu\text{A}$ for undoped, Mg-doped, and Si-doped GaN samples, respectively. The EPSC evolution is depicted in five stages, indicated by purple, yellow, green, blue, and red dots in Figure 2a–c. Furthermore, **Figure 3** illustrates the energy band structures associated with the EPSC phenomenon for these GaN samples to understand the working mechanism of the optoelectronic synapse. Stage 1 (marked with purple dots in Figure 2) is in the initial state; when the light source is turned on, electrons are excited from the valence band to the conduction band, as shown in Figure 3a,c,e, and the current of all three samples increases rapidly to reach Stage 2 (marked with yellow dots in Figure 2). In Stage 3 (marked with green dots in Figure 2), owing to the existence of defect energy levels in the sample, some of the photogenerated carriers are trapped by the defective capture centers, and a dynamic equilibrium process of trapping and de-trapping occurs. Because there were more defect energy levels in the Si-doped GaN sample than in the other two samples, the current increased slowly. In contrast, for the undoped and Mg-doped samples, the current basically remained at a constant level during this stage and changed little. When the light is turned off in Stage 4 (marked with blue dots in Figure 2), the photo-generated electron–hole pairs start to recombine, as shown in Figure 3b,d,f, and the current decreases rapidly. Furthermore, in Stage 5 (marked with red dots in Figure 2), the trapped carriers were released, which slowed down the current recovery rate. By comparing the three samples, we can observe that the EPSC decayed rapidly to a near-zero value for the undoped and Mg-doped samples. However, for Si-doped GaN sample, the EPSC decayed gradually and the value of EPSC decreased to 37.9% after 30 s while only to 2.6 and 10.9% for undoped and Mg-doped samples, respectively (as indicated by the red star position in Figure 2a–c. This is closely related to a greater number of defects involving impurities that cause deep-level states,

which agrees with the Raman and PL spectra. The greater the amount of carriers being trapped and the more time needed for their transport, the longer the resulting decay time.

Furthermore, the decay behavior of the light-activated synaptic device can be described by the Kohlrausch-stretched exponential function, as follows^[26]

$$I = I_r \times \exp \left[- \left(\frac{t}{\tau} \right)^\beta \right] \quad (1)$$

where I denotes the device's current at t , I_r represents the device's current value after removing the optical stimulus, τ signifies the chirality time constant, and β indicates an exponent ranging from 0 to 1.^[26]

The inset graphs in Figure 2a–c show the fitting results using the Kohlrausch-stretched exponential function after removing the 360 nm light simulation pulses. The decay times were 30, 0.66, and 0.4 s for the Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN samples, respectively. We also investigated the EPSC characteristics of different samples with a light excitation duration of 50 s, as illustrated in Figure S3, Supporting Information, for the Si-doped GaN sample. The decay times were found to be 163, 1.5, and 0.44 s for the Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN samples, respectively. The EPSC decayed to 47% after 100 s for the Si-doped GaN sample, whereas it decayed to only 24 and 2% for the Mg-doped and undoped GaN samples, respectively. The greater the decay time τ , the more gradual the decay process. Based on the comparison of EPSC behavior, it can be logically deduced that Si-doped GaN is the most effective for synaptic devices, owing to its more prominent trapping processes during illumination.^[15a,27]

Synaptic plasticity serves as a critical neurochemical basis for learning and memory in neuroscience, thought to arise from STP and LTP within the human brain.^[25,28] PPF is a key STP mechanism in biological systems, essential for processing temporal information in auditory visual signals. When a synapse experiences two closely spaced presynaptic spikes, the subsequent postsynaptic response is amplified, resulting in a larger EPSC compared to the first. The PPF index is defined as the ratio of A2 to A1, where A1 and A2 denote the amplitudes of the

Figure 3. The energy band structures of EPSC phenomenon for different samples. a,c), and e) are the energy band diagrams of undoped, Mg-doped, and Si-doped GaN TFs under light stimulation, respectively. b,d), and f) are the energy band diagrams of undoped, Mg-doped, and Si doped TFs without light stimulation, respectively. The rose–red ball and blue ball indicate the electron and hole, respectively. The green arrows signify the trapping and de-trapping process, while transparent red and blue balls signify the disappeared electron and hole, respectively.

Figure 4. Photo response by two consecutive pulses data for a) undoped, b) Mg-doped, and c) Si-doped GaN TFs. d) PPF index at diverse time intervals.

EPSCs elicited by the first and second light stimuli, respectively.^[29] Figure 4a–c shows the PPF effect induced by two consecutive spikes of 360 nm wavelength light, each with a duration of 1 s and separated by a 1 s interval, for undoped, Mg-doped, and Si-doped GaN samples, respectively. The experimental results for the artificial synapse clearly demonstrated PPF behavior in the Si-doped GaN samples, while little to no PPF behavior was observed in the Mg-doped and undoped GaN samples. The PPF index for the Si-doped GaN was 173% with a spike duration of 1 s, decreasing to 134% as the pulse interval increased to 8 s. The PPF response in the Si-doped GaN closely resembled that of biological synapses, indicating the device’s strong capability to mimic biological synaptic behavior. This characteristic is crucial for encoding temporal information in auditory and visual signals. As displayed in Figure 4d, a clear correlation exists between the PPF index and the interval between consecutive light pulses in the Si-doped GaN sample. The shorter the interval, the higher the PPF index, aligning with the time-dependent behavior of the PPF index in biological synapses.^[15a,30] The A2/A1 decay curve as a function of the time interval can be modeled by a double exponential function described by the following equation^[31]

$$\text{PPF} = 1 + C_1 \exp(\Delta t / \tau_1) + C_2 \exp(\Delta t / \tau_2) \quad (2)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are fitting constants, and τ_1 and τ_2 represent the characteristic relaxation times for fast and slow decay processes, respectively. τ_1 corresponds to the rapid decrease in photocurrent

due to the recombination of carriers associated with inter-band transitions, while τ_2 reflects the slower decline in photocurrent caused by carrier trapping related to defect-associated transitions.^[32] The time interval significantly influences the PPF index, with the two showing a strong correlation (Figure 4d). These findings further confirm that our proposed device has an exceptional ability to emulate the behavior of biological synapses.

Biological neural systems exhibit two fundamental types of memory behavior: STM and LTM. STM generally lasts only a few milliseconds to several seconds before fading, whereas LTM can endure for seconds to years. Through repeated training and rehearsal, STM can be converted into LTM.^[33] This transition in the Si-doped GaN device was accomplished by applying pulsed UV light stimulation with varying light durations, frequencies, intensities, and pulse numbers. As displayed in Figure 5a, increasing the light duration from 1 to 10 s caused the EPSC to rise from 43 to 206 nA, while the extracted relaxation time extended from 7 to 29 s (Figure S4, Supporting Information). This indicates the transition from STM to LTM. By varying the frequency of light stimulation from 0.05 to 0.25 Hz (Figure 5b), the EPSC increased from 14 to 51 nA, further demonstrating the transition from STM to LTM. Moreover, this transition could be achieved with varying intensities and pulse numbers, as displayed in Figure 5c,d. Both the intensity and pulse number of light stimulation were found to significantly enhance the EPSC from weak (STM) to strong (LTM) states. Specifically, increasing the light intensity from

Figure 5. The transition from STM to LTM due to a) lighting duration, b) frequency, c) intensity, and d) pulse number for the Si-doped GaN device.

1.33 to 2.67 to 5.33 mW cm^{-2} resulted in higher current values of 17.0, 24.9, and 37.3 nA, respectively. The extracted relaxation times, fitted using Equation (1), increased from 45 to 57 s. Furthermore, varying the pulse number of light stimulation from 5 to 30 pulses led to an increase in EPSC from 31.6 to 89.0 nA, with the relaxation time extending from 46 to 290 s. These findings strongly indicate the transition from STM to LTM, demonstrating a compelling mimicry of biological excitatory synapses.

Neuromorphic computing, inspired by the human brain, offers the advantage of low energy consumption.^[18] Therefore, energy consumption is a crucial metric for assessing the performance of synaptic devices and can be determined as follows

$$\int_{t_0}^{t_1} V \times I(x) dx \quad (3)$$

where t_0 and t_1 represent the times that the light is turned on and off, respectively, V indicates the working voltage, and I denotes the response current of the device. In the human brain, the energy expenditure per synaptic event is 10^{-15} – 10^{-13} J.^[15a] **Figure 6a** shows the energy consumption behavior of Si-doped GaN TFs. The energy consumption was calculated to be 4.96×10^{-11} J, with a pulse width and voltage of 1 s and 0.01 V, respectively. Notably, energy consumption can be reduced by utilizing light with lower intensity and fewer pulses. By fine-tuning

Figure 6. a) The energy consumption associated with a single optical pulse. b) The use of continuous light pulses to replicate the learning and experience behavior of the human brain.

and optimizing various parameters, lower energy consumption can be achieved. Compared to other synaptic devices based on GaN materials, our devices demonstrate energy consumption levels that are close to those of the human brain.^[15a,27]

Humans develop cognitive understanding through learning-experience behaviors, which encompass learning, forgetting, and relearning processes.^[34] During the “relearning” phase, the brain requires less energy and time to process information compared to the initial “learning” phase.^[35] To investigate the device’s ability to simulate human-brain-learning behavior, we examined the EPSC response of the Si-doped GaN device triggered by 360 nm UV light with 25 light pulses (1.33 mW cm^{-2} , 5 s duration, 5 s interval), as shown in Figure 6b. The EPSC progressively increased with continuous UV light irradiation, with the EPSC value on the 25th pulse nearly three times greater than that of the first pulse. During the initial learning phase, the EPSC showed a gradual increase. After completing this first learning phase, a forgetting phase ensued, characterized by a current decay over 100 s, where the current gradually decreased from 27.1 to 16.9 nA, rather than dropping immediately to the initial value. This behavior resembles the gradual forgetting observed in human brains. Following the removal of light stimulation, the EPSC value decreased to a certain level (first forgetting). In the subsequent learning phase (second learning), using only five light pulses, the EPSC value reached the same level achieved with 10 pulses during the first learning phase. In the third learning phase, with just two light pulses, the EPSC value increased to an even higher memory level.

Building on this, we further explored the application of learning-experience behaviors in image memorization, as shown in Figure 7. The image of the “SZLAB” letters was encoded using different light intensities as input stimuli. The letter was recorded by measuring changes in the EPSC at various time points, with a light duration and interval of 2 s and a fixed

number of repetitive stimulations set at 25 (see Figure S5, Supporting Information). After a 100 s saving phase, the color contrast of the dot array strengthened, paralleling similar processes observed in human brains. Subsequently, we simulated the dynamic forgetting process, finding that after 100 s of forgetting, the color contrast of the dot array diminished. These results suggest that the Si-doped GaN neuromorphic sensor array demonstrates excellent image memory capabilities. Overall, the observed visual storage and forgetting behaviors closely align with those of human visual perception.

3. Conclusions

In summary, Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN TFs were fabricated on (0001) sapphire substrates via MOCVD. Subsequently, two-terminal optoelectronic artificial synapse devices were designed and fabricated based on an MSM structure. Notable PPC behavior was observed for the Si-doped GaN device compared to that for the undoped and Mg-doped GaN devices. Synaptic functions, such as PPF, STM, LTM, and the transition from STM to LTM could be obtained by applying UV light pulse stimulation. Furthermore, human learning-experience behaviors, visual recognition, and memorization were emulated using our artificial synaptic device. Thus, this study presents an effective approach for designing photonic synapses with GaN-based materials in the fields of neuromorphic computing and bio-realistic artificial intelligence.

4. Experimental Section

Sample Fabrication and Preparation: Si-doped, Mg-doped, and undoped GaN were grown on (0001) c-plane sapphire substrates using MOCVD. Trimethylgallium (TMGa), bis(cyclopentadienyl)magnesium (Cp_2Mg),

Figure 7. Modeling the dynamic encoding and decay processes of human visual memory.

monosilane (SiH₄), and ammonia (NH₃) were employed as the Ga, Mg, Si, and N sources, respectively. Hydrogen and nitrogen were utilized as carrier gases. Silicon- and magnesium-doped GaN layers, each ≈2 μm thick, were deposited onto a ≈2 μm undoped GaN buffer layer and a low-temperature GaN nucleation layer. The deposition process occurred at 1100 °C and 2 mm h⁻¹. Following that, an Ag electrode with 100 nm thick was patterned using plasma sputtering equipment at room temperature. The finger length, finger width, and interfinger distance of the interdigital electrode were 3000, 100, and 50 μm, respectively.

Sample Characterization: The thicknesses and doping levels of the Si-GaN and Mg-GaN layers were assessed individually using SIMS (CAMECA, IMS 7f-auto). To determine their crystalline structures, XRD measurement was conducted on the grown films using a Bruker D8 Advance instrument. Raman spectroscopy (Horiba, LabRam HR 800) at room temperature was utilized to determine the structure and stress using a solid-state laser (excitation wavelength = 532 nm). The laser power was concentrated into a spot roughly 1 μm in diameter on the sample. PL measurements at ambient temperature were performed using a HeCd laser with a 325 nm emission wavelength. Surface morphologies were evaluated using tapping-mode atomic force microscopy (Bruker, Dimension icon). A Keithley 6487 source meter was used for all electrical measurements. A 360 nm laser with tunable power and pulse width was employed for illumination.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by Gusu Talent (grant no. ZXL2021383) and the Suzhou Science and Technology Plan Project (grant no. ST202219). M.H.R. thanks the National Natural Science Foundation of China (grant no. 52071225). All the authors contributed to and approved the final version of this manuscript. X.Y. and J.L. contributed equally to this work.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Xiaoqin Yang: data curation (supporting); investigation (lead); writing—original draft (lead); writing—review and editing (lead). **Jiawen Lu:** investigation (lead); validation (lead). **Luyu Zhao:** investigation (supporting). **Xiaorui Han:** data curation (supporting); investigation (supporting). **Zhongwei Bai:** investigation (supporting). **Peiwen Quan:** investigation (supporting). **Liangshuai Xie:** investigation (supporting). **Liang Li:** investigation (supporting); validation (supporting). **Haoxuan Sun:** investigation (supporting); methodology (supporting). **Mark Hermann Rummeli:** writing—original draft (supporting); writing—review and editing (supporting). **Bingcheng Luo:** data curation (supporting); investigation (supporting); writing—original draft (supporting); writing—review and editing (supporting). **Hong Gu:** investigation (supporting); writing—original draft (supporting); writing—review and editing (supporting).

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

artificial synapses, GaN, light-stimulated synaptic devices, metal-organic chemical vapor depositions, persistent photoconductivities

Received: August 27, 2024

Revised: November 14, 2024

Published online: January 26, 2025

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